

PARENTING STYLE: ITS EFFECT TO LEARNER'S BEHAVIOR

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 10

Pages: 1226-1233

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2427

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13860195

Manuscript Accepted: 07-26-2024

Parenting Style: Its Effect to Learner's Behavior

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Abstract

Learners' behavior is basically an offshoot of the environment and effect different factors which include parenting. This study determined the Parenting Style of the parents and its effect on the behavior of the learners. Data were statistically treated with the suitable statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation, frequency and percentage Distribution, and Cramer's V. The respondents are learners and teachers from Dansalan Annex Elementary School located at Dansalan, Sapad, Lanao del Norte. The researcher used Parenting Style and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ) and Children Behavior Checklist (CBC). Results showed that the respondents had experienced an authoritative way of parenting and revealed to have positive effect on the behavior of the learners. It revealed that there is a significant relationship between the authoritative, permissive, and uninvolved parenting to the learner's behavior. In contrast, authoritarian, has no significant relationship on the behavior of the learners. It is therefore recommended that the participation and support from the parents is needed in establishing a positive outcome in terms in the behavioral development of the learners and linked to have an influence on their academic performance.

Keywords: *parenting style, behavioral development, parental support*

Introduction

Behavior problem that interfere in teaching and learning is one of the biggest challenges faced by most of the teachers in today's classroom. Tracking back the educational system years ago, where they have good manner and right conduct in their curricula is linked to lessen the behavioral problem and issues of the learners. This is because parents are obliged to support and to teach the right things and good to acquire a good performance in school. The subject also motivates parents to use proper and positive parenting style towards their children. Now, most learners are likely to engage in different behavioral problem and issues in school basically because parents lack of support and guidance on their children.

Parents play an important role in the child's behavior. This can have a positive and/or negative effect as regards to the emotions and traits of the children especially on the parenting style that they portrait on their children. Children tend to behave in accordance to the treatment and behavior that parents display at home. Thus, parents as a first teacher must exhibit good characters and show support to attain good outcome in terms of behavior.

In addition, a good parenting style and responsible parenting influence the learners in terms of adapting a good behavior. Therefore, nurturing a child and showing them the right things to do especially at home will help learners to achieve satisfaction and success.

According to Erickson (2017), parents extremely influence the behavior of their children. Children are comparable to sponges--they imitate and model everything what they observed and integrate it to their lives. He presumed that the vital role of a parents to set a good examples for their children. Undesirable examples can be harmful to a child's development and may result to a bad performance.

In addition, according to Moore (2017), it is how you react and discipline your children significantly affects how they improve, both cognitively and socially. The development of a child is influence by different adaptation he acquires in people around him and to his surroundings. Parents as the first caregiver, tend to have the most significant influence on the child's development both positive and negative.

The researcher intended to determine the effect of parenting style in the behavior of the learners as it is observed by the teachers. This aimed to conduct the learners of Dansalan Annex Elementary School located at Dansalan, Sapad, Lanao del Norte. Furthermore, it was believed that the study was conducted on the second semester of the school year 2018-2109. With the above presentation, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study on the parenting style as to its effect in the behavior of the learners, because, there was a behavior issues in which teachers alone cannot directly diminished without the participation and support of the parents.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the effects of different parenting styles on the learners' behavior of Dansalan Annex Elementary School learners as for the School Year 2018-2019. This study strived to answer the following questions:

1. What are the parenting styles as observed by learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. authoritative;
 - 1.2. authoritarian;
 - 1.3. permissive; and
 - 1.4. uninvolved?
2. What are the learners' behavioral problems observed by the teachers in the classroom/ school??

3. Is there any significant effect in the learners' behavior on the following parenting style:
 - 3.1. authoritative;
 - 3.2. authoritarian;
 - 3.3. permissive; and
 - 3.4. uninvolved/neglectful?
4. What program can be designed based on the result of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational research design since it portrays the relationship between parenting style and the behavior of the learners. Descriptive-Correlational designs because it allows correlating two variables that can indicate the effect of parenting style to the behavior of the learner as the result.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were randomly selected 70 learners of Dansalan Annex Elementary School. Learners of Dansalan Annex Elementary School were the primary respondent of the study because the researcher believed that there are such behavioral problem that the teachers' alone cannot help without the support from the parents. For the learner's behavior, the teacher would be the one answering the questionnaire as based on their observation on the behavior of their learner towards other in school/classroom. The researcher used the random sampling in selecting the respondent.

Table 1. *Distribution of respondents per Grade level*

Respondent	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5	Grade 6
Learner	9	12	10	13	11	15
Teacher	1	1	1	1	1	1

Instrument

Table 1 shows the respondents distribution per Grade level. The researcher adapts some questionnaire related to parenting style and made some revision. The parenting style questionnaire was adapted from The Parenting Style and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ) and for the pupils' questionnaire, it was adapted from the Child Behavior Checklist (CBC). The revised questionnaire has 40- item for the learners and 15-item for pupil's behavior which teacher would be responsible in answering the questionnaire as to what he/she observed on pupils' behavior in classroom school. The revised questionnaire would be submitted to the adviser for the approval and validation.

Procedure

The researcher was the one who personally conducted the study and facilitated the gathering of the data. A sincere permission letter was given to the schools division superintendent, principal, and teachers. Moreover, the researcher asked personally the Dean of Graduates Studies of St. Peter's College for the approval of some needed documents for the successful gathering of data.

Upon granting the permission, the researcher proceeds to the school to float the questionnaire. The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the learners during their dismissal time. Moreover, the researcher convinced the respondents that the confidentiality of their answers was rest assured. The researcher personally translated and explained the content/ meaning of the questionnaire to the learners. Upon completing the required respondent for the learners, the researcher approached the teacher to answer the questionnaire about what he observed on the pupils' behavior in the classroom on their vacant time.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to analyze and interpret the data gathered. The following statistical techniques or methods employed to answer correctly the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, Mean and Standard Deviation was used to determine the behavior of the pupil in the school as to the parental style used by parents. For Problem 2, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to determine the behavior of pupils in the classroom. For Problem 3, Cramer's V was used to identify the relationship between parenting style and the pupils' behavior.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result/ and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1. What is the parenting style as observed by the learners in terms of authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and uninvolved?

Table 2 demonstrates the parents' strict parenting approach. The findings indicate that the majority of students gave a mean score of 3.11 when asked about parenting styles they have encountered from their parents. According to the results, the majority of respondents

believed their parents supported and loved them, indicating that they were raised in an authoritative manner. The outcome also showed that students raised with this parenting style are probably going to place a high priority on obeying and respecting their parents.

Table 2. *Authoritative Parenting Style*

<i>Authoritative</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My parents explain the consequences of my behavior.	3.21	Sometimes
2. My parents encourage me to talk about my troubles.	3.04	Sometimes
3. My parents help me to understand the impact of behavior by encouraging me to talk about the consequences of my own actions.	3.14	Sometimes
4. My parents explain how they feel about my good and bad behavior.	3.14	Sometimes
5. My parents give me reasons why rules should be obeyed.	3.16	Sometimes
6. My parents give praise when I do well.	3.04	Sometimes
7. My parents show respect for my opinions by encouraging me to express them.	3.06	Sometimes
8. My parents give comfort and understand when I am upset.	3.09	Sometimes
9. My parents have a warm and intimate times with us.	3.09	Sometimes
10. My parents is responsive to my feelings or needs.	3.13	Sometimes
General Mean	3.11	Sometimes

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Never

The result is the same with the study of Alizadeh, Abu Talib, Abdullah, and Mansor (2011), which they concluded that authoritative parenting style continues to influence children's development in positive ways beyond childhood and also adolescence. Conceptually, the authoritative style parents have both responsive and demanding dimensions. Their children have fewer behavioral problems and a high rate of academic achievement in school.

In addition, as cited by Sarwar (2016), parents that are authoritative usually provide children with advice in an appropriate manner. This approach also requires parents to have the patience necessary to explain to a child the repercussions of their actions (Larzelere, Morris & Harrist, 2013).

Table 3. *Authoritarian Style of Parenting*

<i>Authoritarian</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My parents scold or criticize me when my behavior doesn't meet their expectations.	1.64	Never
2. My parents explode anger towards me.	1.74	Never
3. My parents grab me when I am being disobedient.	1.60	Never
4. My parents yell or shout at me when I misbehaved.	1.77	Seldom
5. My parents use physical punishment a way of disciplining.	1.80	Seldom
6. My parents slap me when I am misbehaving.	1.61	Never
7. My parents spank me when I am being disobedient.	1.79	Seldom
8. My parents scold or criticize me for my improvement.	1.67	Never
9. When I asks why I has to conform, their statement is, "because I said so, " or "I am the parent and I want you to."	1.79	Seldom
10. My parents cut off my allowances when I misbehaved.	1.90	Seldom
General Mean	1.73	Never

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Never

Table 3 presents the authoritarian way of parenting as a portrait by the parents to their children. The result shows that most of the respondents seldom experienced the authoritarian way of parenting. Indicator (14, 15, 17, 19 & 20) shows that parents at once used an authoritarian practices which they occasionally punished their children like spanking, yelling and cutting off their allowances. This means that children have experienced unhappy, controlling, and lack of support from their parents. The outcome is consistent with Miller's (2010) claimed that youngsters frequently exhibit low self-esteem, poor social skills, rage, and greater rates of anxiety and despair. Furthermore, even though they might continue to comply, they might grow to distrust authority in general.

The researcher thought that instead of using physical punishment, disciplinary action could be a way to help them understand and appreciate one another as well as teach them appropriate behavior, particularly at home. As a result, the best way to teach children is to set an example for them by treating them with kindness and understanding. really, studies reveal that disciplining children really makes them misbehave more (Markham, 2014).

Table 4 illustrates the permissive way of parenting showed by the parents on their children. The result showed that the permissive parenting wasnot really experienced by the learners, which means, learners have no authority in doing what they want and cannot make decisions without the consent from their parents.

There is at least one indicator (25) showed that the learners seldom experienced that their parents give into when they committed commotion, which means, parents take the responsibility when their children is misbehaving and this may have a negative effect on the learners such as lack of self-discipline and less responsible.

This result is similar to the statement of Cherry (2008), children with permissive parents often lack self-control, have weak social skills, can be demanding and self-absorbed, and can feel insecure since there aren't enough rules or boundaries in place.

Table 4. *Permissive Parenting Style*

<i>Permissive</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My parents spoiled me.	1.71	Never
2. My parents take into account my preferences in making plans for the family.	1.49	Never
3. My parents take my desires into account before asking me to do something.	1.54	Never
4. My parents encourage me to freely express myself even when disagreeing them.	1.60	Never
5. My parents give into when I causes a commotion about something.	1.94	Seldom
6. My parents allow me to give input into family rules.	1.54	Never
7. My parents find difficulty on how to discipline me.	1.46	Never
8. My parents allow me to answer them in a bad manner.	1.63	Never
9. My parents allow me to watch any movies.	1.70	Never
10. My parents tolerate me when I act inappropriate to other or elders.	1.37	Never
General Mean	1.60	Never

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Never

Table 5 present the uninvolved/ neglectful parenting style. The result implied that some learners felt that they occasionally suffered from an uninvolved parent, which means, they were sometimes neglected by their parents in the indicator (32, 33, 38, & 40). This describe that learners can develop depression, lack of social interaction and lack of self-confident.

Table 5. *Uninvolved/ Neglectful Parenting Style*

<i>Uninvolved/ Neglectful</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My parents state punishments and do not actually do them.	1.47	Never
2. My parents threaten me with punishment more often than actually giving it.	1.76	Seldom
3. My parents use threats as punishment with little or no justification.	1.86	Seldom
4. My parents punish by taking privileges away from me with little or no explanations.	1.47	Never
5. My parents punish by putting me off somewhere alone with little or no explanations.	1.69	Never
6. My parents don't discipline me much.	1.71	Never
7. My parents don't take into an action when I am misbehaving.	1.64	Never
8. My parents leave me all alone at home.	2.04	Seldom
9. My parents don't care enough about me whether I do good things or not.	1.43	Never
10. My parents don't listen to my reasons when I commit mistakes.	1.94	Seldom
General Mean	1.70	Never

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Never

An uninvolved parenting style is regarded as the worst of the four primary parenting philosophies because it ignores a child's basic need for love, acceptance, and care. Children of absentee parents lack discipline and appropriate limits because they receive little attention from their parents (Regain, 2018).

Table 6. *Summary of Parenting Style*

<i>Parenting Style</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Authoritative	3.11	Sometimes
Authoritarian	1.73	Never
Permissive	1.60	Never
Uninvolved	1.70	Never

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Never

As shown in Table 6, the majority of students indicated that they occasionally took into account the mean average of (3.11) when describing the parenting style they get, which is consistent with an authoritative parenting style. The outcome unequivocally shows that the learner's conduct and the parenting style are related. Furthermore, this suggests that these parents provide for their children's needs, spend meaningful time with them, and demonstrate appropriate caregiving. This suggests that students who experience authoritative parenting will have better, more prosperous, and happier lives overall. Similar to the study of Santiago (2017), there exists a statistically significant correlation between the authoritative parenting style and the self-esteem levels of the underprivileged respondents.

The authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved revealed that this parenting style is less experience by the learners. This implies that learners of Dansalan Annex Elementary School are less inclined to partake in any misbehavior act and wrong-doings.

Problem 2. What are the learners' behavioral problems observed by the teachers in the classroom/ school?

Table 7 presents the learners' behavioral problem. It indicates that there were two indicators where a behavioral problem occurred. Indicator (6), which learners often demand much more attention. This implies that at once, learners showed unnecessary behavior that can or may disturb the teaching process. Indicator (7), which learner's shows poor school work. This may be an indicator that learners have experienced less support in terms of schooling.

Therefore, parents have to support and give time in terms of school assignments, projects and school activities that their children may motivated in attending and doing their school works. Encouragement, motivation and support is needed for the learners to strive for a

better academic performance.

Table 7. Learners' Behavioral Problem

Learners' Behavioral Problem		Mean	Description
1.	Clingy to adults or too dependent.	1.47	Never Observed
2.	Cruel, bully or mean to others.	1.60	Never Observed
3.	Doesn't get along with other kids.	1.64	Never Observed
4.	Would rather be alone than with others.	1.69	Never Observed
5.	Too shy or timid.	1.73	Never Observed
6.	Demands a lot of attention.	1.81	Often Observed
7.	Poor school work.	2.06	Often Observed
8.	Can't sit still, restless or hyperactive.	1.66	Never Observed
9.	Lying or cheating.	1.39	Never Observed
10.	Too fearful or anxious.	1.34	Never Observed
11.	Vandalize	1.23	Never Observed
12.	Truant, skips school	1.50	Never Observed
13.	Disobedient in school	1.49	Never Observed
14.	Breaks rules at home, school, or elsewhere.	1.36	Never Observed
15.	Fears in going to school.	1.26	Never Observed
Average		1.55	Never Observed

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Observed; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes Observed; 1.75-2.49, Often Observed; 1.00-1.74, Never Observed

Despite of the two behavioral problem observed, the result revealed that the leaners of Dansalan Annex Elementary School have less behavioral problem. This describe that learners have satisfaction in the parenting practices of their parents.

The finding of the study suggests that there is definite effect of parenting style on the child behavior and parents of the studied generation prefer communication over harsh punishment, love over hate and support their children for getting effective confidence.

Parenting style does, in fact, appear to have an impact on children's behavior, according to a study by Zaman, Arslan, Malik, and Mehmood (2014). The parents in this generation value communication over severe punishment, love over hate, and support for their children to develop effective confidence.

Problem 3. Is there any significant effect in the learners' behavior on the following parenting styleauthoritative, authoritarian, permissive and uninvolved?

Table 8. Effect in the Learners' Behavior as to Their Parenting Style

	df	Computed X2	Tabled X2	Level of Significance	Decision
Authoritative	4	18.224	9.488	Sig.	Reject H0
Authoritarian	6	6.778	12.592	Not Sig.	Accept H0
Permissive	4	10.872	9.488	Sig.	Reject H0
Uninvolved/Neglectful	4	11.014	9.488	Sig.	Reject H0

Table 8 demonstrates how the learner's conduct is impacted by the parenting style. The findings indicate that, according to the teacher's observations, an authoritarian parenting style had no discernible effect on the behavior of the students. This contrasts with authoritarian, lenient, and detached parenting, which has a major impact on students' conduct. All things considered, the authoritative parenting style is the most important one that has been shown to influence the behavior of the learners.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The parenting style of the parents had a significant effect on the learners' behavior. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there was no significant effect between the levelof parenting style and the behavior of the learners was rejected in terms of authoritative, permissive and uninvolved parenting style. This mean that having an authoritative, permissive and uninvolved parenting has an effect on the behavior of the learners. And among all, authoritative parenting style has concluded to be the most applied practices used by the parents. In regards to the behavior of the learners, a less behavioral problem where identified. Thus, the authoritative parenting style has a positive effect on how learners behaved.

In contrast, the authoritarian parenting style was accepted, which implied that authoritarian parenting has no significant effect on the learners' behavior.

Based on the conclusions made in the study, the following recommendations were set forth to the following:

For the School Administrators, that they may recommend and to encourage parents to attend, to involve and to participate in different school activities. Working with parents also helps learners to improve their behavioral condition. They may also establish different programs to carefully monitor those having a behavioral problem inside the school or in the classrooms.

For the Teachers that they may work with the parents in establishing a good environment where learners feel that they are accepted loved and secured. They may encourage parents to administer a responsible and supportive parenting style especially at home. In addition, during HPTA/ GPTA meetings, teachers have to enlighten parents that using positive phrases will motivate learners to do right things and thus, positive behavior may be possible.

For the Parents that they may encourage to display a good behavior / manner in front of their children as they are the best and first teacher of their children. They play a vital role in the overall development of their children, therefore, encouraging motivating and providing the needs of their children will create a success in children's life. In addition, they are also advised to use positive reinforcement instead of using harsh and physical punishment.

For the Learners, they may encourage to do good things not just inside the school/ classroom but also in different settings. Learners also advised to show goodness in itself, so that, those that surrounds the may adapt it.

For the Future Researchers, they may suggest in conducting a similar study which focuses on the proper parenting style as to its impact on the academic performance of the learners and to their holistic development.

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